

Utilization of Computer-Aided Instructional Strategies in Teaching Technology and Livelihood Education

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Abstract

This study aimed to determine the effectiveness of computer-aided instructional strategies used by the Technology and Livelihood Education teachers in the Second Congressional District of Schools Division Office I Pangasinan. This study used the descriptive and developmental method of research to ascertain the utilization of the computer-aided instructional strategies. The sources of data will be taken from the analysis of the responses of the respondents and the result of the test results and responses of the teachers from the given questionnaire.

As this is Descriptive research, the study shall describe existing situations and conditions relative to the study which included a total number of 80 learner-respondents, 80 teacher-respondents, and 24 instructional leaders which are randomly selected. The needed data were obtained from the teacher-made assessments to measure the academic performance of the learners and a validated questionnaire. Thorough interpretation of the participants' answers shaped the findings of this study. After the gathering of data, the researcher able to find out the effectiveness of using the computer-aided instructional strategies by the TLE teachers and instructional leaders able to find out the performance level of the respondents.

It was found out that respondents of this investigation are 80 Technology and Livelihood Education learners, 80 teachers in TLE, and 24 instructional leaders who are randomly selected from the Second Congressional District in the Schools Division Office I of Pangasinan. Data revealed that 43 of the respondents coming from the total of 80 are MA Degree holders, 67 are TLE majors, 53 are of 11-15 years of teaching experience, and 61 of them attended 4-6 seminars/trainings. Data shows on instructional leaders showed that 22 out of the 24 respondents are highly educated, with a Doctorate or master's degree, 22 out of 24 have more than 11 years, 7-9 seminars/trainings, with 10 instructional leaders, but 7 instructional leaders have limited exposure to training, indicating there may be areas of growth where an increase can be made in ongoing professional growth. The level of competency of Technology and Livelihood Education teachers is described as "Advanced" which means, TLE teachers have mastery in using the computer-aided instructional strategies which is a necessary tool in helping and improving the academic performance of the learners. The level of utilization of Computer-Aided Instructional Strategies is described as "moderately practiced" with an average weighted mean of 2.94. This entails that teachers are capable and knowledgeable in using computer-aided instructional strategies. The performance level of the learners in Technology and Livelihood Education was described as "mastered". There is no significant relationship between the performance of the students and the level of utilization of Computer-Aided Instructional strategies applied by their teachers. A Capability Building Program was proposed to improve the performance of the learners.

Chapter I

The Problem

Rationale: Technologies are a part of our world and are used by us every day. They are a valuable resource for knowledge about ourselves, others, and regional and international events. They assist us in all aspects of our research. Our daily responsibilities and commitments are often made simpler by them. But most crucially,

they support us in engaging in more beneficial and inclusive global competition. Computers can also help learners visualize objects that are difficult or impossible to see.

The best thing about digital learning is the availability of study materials in a range of formats. Students can study in a variety of ways by accessing digital learning materials, such as blogs, podcasts, webinars, live online classes, and video lectures. Thanks to these digital learning resources, students can learn at their own pace and develop their own learning preferences. This came about as a result of the changes and updates that the world's knowledge of students has to provide. The use of instructional films today is currently only beginning to meet the needs of both today's and tomorrow's learners. They are used by teachers and even by students to research, contrast, and comprehend many subjects. The usage of movies in the classroom is nothing new.

The modernization of education brought on by the reform of the curriculum in our educational system has had a considerable impact on the accessibility of high-quality education. As part of the Department of Education's digital rise program, it opens doors for the nippy needs of the students to further prolong their attention span in the teaching-learning process. One such implementation is the implementation of extending the accessibility and convenience of our instructional materials, known as the Open Educational Resources.

These days, using computers and other electronic-related technology is becoming more and more of a need. People are required to use technology in the majority of employment that exist today, sometimes without even realizing it. In an information society, using these technological advancements is no longer an option for an individual; rather, it is a skill set that all people must have.

It is believed that using computer and multimedia technologies does not always imply relying solely on computers. Access to a wide range of knowledge sources should be permitted for any device used in the classroom. It should help make learning more engaging and fun. For better prospects for constructivist learning, it should instead emphasize both individual and group activity.

The teacher is expected to be more than just a good instructor in today's classroom. In addition, the Junior High School offers a course called Technology and Livelihood Education (TLE) that encourages students to put their newly acquired knowledge into practice in real-world situations. Though, due to the learners' perception that this subject is only for those who are average in level of thought and poor in their academic standing, Technology and Livelihood Education (TLE) is always overlooked and given less emphasis by the learners. This is why students nowadays frequently disregard and take for granted the subjects that TLE teachers teach, not even comprehending the vital role that these subjects play in their daily lives.

There are only a few advantages in computer-aided instruction (CAI) that can compete with the benefits of personalized learning, immediate feedback, and engagement. Means, Toyama, Murphy, Bakia, and Jones (2010) conducted a study for the United States. According to the U.S. Department of Education's findings on successful integration into instructional methodologies: CAI is considered to have an appreciable positive effect on student learning outcomes—students are able to get feedback tailored specifically for them and are also allowed to learn at their own pace which leads to better performance academically.

CAI, or computer-aided instruction, refers to the use of computer technology in educational environments with the aim of making learning easier and more effective. It employs various strategies—like multimedia presentations or interactive software systems—all designed not only to hold students' interest but also help them better comprehend different topics that can be studied through such programs.

The use of technology in the classroom is highly valued in contemporary education since it affects the learning environment and enhances instructional methods. Technology engages students and offers individualized learning experiences that are tailored to their requirements and learning preferences through multimedia content, interactive simulations, and online collaboration. Outside of the traditional classroom, technology also makes it simpler to access a wealth of resources and knowledge, promoting independent study and critical thinking. Students will benefit from this reform, which reflects the demands of the digital world and equips them with vital skills for the workforce of the future. Mishra and Koehler (2006) claim that technology integration allows teachers the opportunity to create innovative, learner-centered environments that link theoretical concepts to real-world applications.

In expansion, agreeing to Rosenberg 2001, in his concept of computer-mediated instruction (CMI), which is related to computer-aided instruction, is the hone of encouraging educating and learning exercises by means of the utilize of advanced innovation and communication advances. In arrange to provide guidelines data,

empower interaction, and move forward learning results in a assortment of instructive settings, it includes the integration of computers, program programs, and web stages.

As cited by Clark and Mayer, 2016, through intelligently mixed media components like movies, recreations, and intuitively tests that capture learners' consideration and persuade them to effectively lock in within the learning prepare, computer-aided instruction advances dynamic engagement.

In addition, Baker and Inventado, 2014, real-time data analysis on students' progress and performance are sent to teachers through computer-aided instruction, enabling focused interventions and better instructional choices.

Numerous advantages of CAI lead to more effective and engaging learning experiences. Its ability to adapt to the needs of various learners is one of its key advantages. Through individualized learning pathways and content, students can proceed at their own rate, completing knowledge gaps and utilizing their strong points. Furthermore, CAI provides prompt feedback, enabling students to identify mistakes and correct them in real-time, enhancing the learning process. A study by Kulik and Kulik (2002) found that CAI interventions frequently result in learning outcomes that are noticeably superior than those produced by traditional teaching tactics.

Limited access to computers and the internet are among the technical issues that contribute to disparities in access to learning materials. Accurate content and pedagogical principles must be carefully considered when creating effective computer-assisted instruction (CAI) products. If a computer-assisted learning product is designed poorly, it may result in perplexity and learning hurdles. According to Levy (2002), educators in a CAI environment should no longer follow their traditional instructional roles but should take on a more advisory and management role. Consequently, they need to undergo continuous training to be able to incorporate technology into their lesson delivery effectively.

The integration of CAI would be highly influential in the field of education. It shifts the function of the teachers from information givers to learning guides. They guide their learners on how to use technology, how to understand data and how to think critically. CAI motivates active learning for students through their ability to investigate, interact with each other, and collaborate through the internet. With the convenience in which users can interact with the instructional information CAI has the capability of ensuring a learning society with the growth of technology.

Through the use of computer-mediated instruction, students can interact with peers, professionals, and resources from across the globe while also collaborating and communicating across geographic boundaries, Palloff, and Pratt, 2013.

Computer-aided instruction is a ground-breaking method of education that makes use of technology to enhance learning chances. It provides benefits like personalized learning routes and quick feedback, but it also has issues like unfair access and a complex architecture that need to be fixed. The educational environment is changing due to CAI, thus instructors must adapt their instructional approaches and job positions. With the development of technology, CAI has the potential to fundamentally modify how we teach and learn, enhancing both the effectiveness and accessibility of education.

The researcher was motivated to conduct this research investigation due to the reason of low academic performance of the grade 9 learners and inadequate knowledge in terms of the actual use of computer technological applications and skills in Technology and Livelihood Education especially for the component in Computer Systems Servicing. The researcher is also the current teacher of Computer Systems Servicing wherein this investigation will of great benefit for the construction of a versatile professional plan for the teachers in the usage of modern technology and uplift the academic performance of those learners who are left behind.

The COVID-19 pandemic has accelerated an unprecedented surge in technology use in education, leading to creativity and the transformation of instructional strategies. With the rise of distance and online learning, teachers have also resorted to using different digital tools and applications for online classrooms, group work, and interactive assessments. This change has sped up the use of technology in learning environments and inspired teachers to become more creative in engaging students in various learning environments. According to Hodges et al. (2020), the pandemic has led educators to use technology in creative ways that enhanced teaching methodologies and pushed the limits of traditional education.

Garrison and Kanuka (2004) conducted an important study on computer-mediated instruction in which they looked at the transformative potential of blended learning in higher education. Their study focused on the

advantages of computer-mediated components in improving learning outcomes when face-to-face and online training are combined. They emphasized the interactive and adaptable aspects of blended learning, arguing that it has the potential to rethink conventional teaching strategies and include students in a more engaging learning environment.

As teachers of this subject that students most often despise, we need to recognize and identify the best strategies or teaching materials for our students to keep them focused, learning, and engaged. enjoyable time. It is helpful to know which of the different ways learners are most comfortable. This prompted researchers to conduct a study on how computer-aided instruction strategies can improve learners' abilities and skills in Technology and Livelihood Education.

Theoretical Framework

This research investigation is closely related to the following below-cited theories to better understand the concept ahead.

Sweller's Cognitive Load Theory suggests that instructional materials should be designed to minimize demands on students' working memories in order to free up processing capacity for learning. In the context of CAI, it suggests that the way in which the information is presented should minimize cognitive overload, so that students are free to focus on understanding and integrating new ideas. Interactive CAI applications can optimize cognitive load by offering scaffolds, feedback, and content sequencing. Designing CAI applications with the concepts of cognitive load, teachers should help students learn how to understand and remember complex content.

Constructivist Learning Theory holds that the student actively constructs information as he interacts with the environment. It was developed through the work of Piaget and Vygotsky. In the context of CAI, such is the concept of creating value by engaging students in meaningful, authentic activity. CAI can assist and support constructivist learning through such features as interactive simulation, scenarios used for problem-solving, and collaborative online settings that invite students to explore, experiment, and understand more deeply. Constructivist CAI promotes the better conceptual understanding and activity in the user.

A special application of Michael G. Moore's Computer-mediated instruction is **Transactional Distance Theory (TDT)**. TDT addresses the psychological and communication constraints in online learning and especially deals with the interaction of learner independence and structure. TDT holds that technology may help reduce the transactional gap in computer-mediated instruction by providing opportunities for contact, collaboration, and prompt feedback. To close the transactional gap and create a successful learning experience, Moore's theory points to the importance of designing online courses that provide for learner control while at the same time embodying sound instructional design.

Constructivism is a learning theory conceptualized by George Siemens in 2005. A lot of what this connects to is computer-aided training. This perspective holds that learning is not only an internal function but is also deeply coupled with the external network of connections and information available through digital technologies. When related to computer-mediated learning, connectivism stresses the importance of enabling learners to search and synthesize the huge volumes of information presented to them on the internet. It underlines how important technology is in terms of making connections, building collaboration, and inculcating the much-needed critical digital literacy skills for all successful learning in today's networked society.

Deci and Ryan, in 2000, proposed the **Self-Determination Theory**, which makes very important implications for computer-based instruction. It states that from the time a student is born, he or she possesses a psychological need for relatedness, competence, and autonomy. SDT emphasizes that the learning process be designed in a way that will support the feelings of autonomy and competence of the learners in making choices, goal-setting, and experiencing mastery within the computer-mediated instruction. The feeling of relatedness with peers and instructors can be facilitated through the computer-mediated training tools, which enable collaboration. Finally, this, in turn, can foster motivation, engagement, and the quality of learning experiences.

Conceptual Framework

The Department of Education's main goal is to deliver high-quality instruction. To improve the teaching and learning process, it is important to highlight how effectively teachers use ICT resources. In order to guarantee

Technology and Livelihood Education teachers' instructional efficacy in the face of technological advancement, the foundation of this research is assessment.

The aforementioned arguments claim that if a teacher only used textbooks, learning would be poor. Even learning becomes more imaginative and meaningful when she uses additional materials that engage the kids' brains. The teacher is in the best position since she works closely with the students to improve or change the curriculum. He is able to select the best instructional resources for them since she is close to them and is aware of their requirements, preferences, and skills.

The following initiatives are supported by **Republic Act No. 10844**, also known as the Department of Information and Communications Technology Act of 2015: Nation building Through ICT, Information Protection, and ICT Advancement in the Philippines. This will help students who study ICT and anything else connected, perhaps in the areas of information and research. Another benefit is that it supports the enhancement of important public services such as education, public health and safety, revenue generation, and socio-civic purposes through the use of ICT. It also supports the promotion of digital literacy, ICT expertise, and knowledge-building among citizens to enable them to participate and compete in an evolving ICT age.

Guidelines on the Implementation of the DepEd Computerization Program (DCP) are outlined in **Department of Education Order 78, Series 2010**. With these technologies, public schools will be better equipped to fulfill the demands of the twenty-first century and improve the teaching-learning process. By giving public schools hardware, software, and instruction in basic troubleshooting, this program will address the backlog of computers in those institutions. The DepEd Computerization Program consists of the following: 1. provide secondary schools with computer lab packages; 2. offer elementary schools an online classroom; 3. Provide mobile teachers with laptop computers; 4. ICT integration in the educational system; 5. Improve the ICT literacy of students, students, students, teachers, and school administrators; and 6. Reduce the public schools' computer backlog.

Department of Education Order 76, Series 2011 – National Adoption and Implementation of the Learning Resources Management and Development System (LRMDS) This order includes the following: 1. information on quantity, quality, and location of textbooks and supplementary materials, and other teaching-learning resources; 2. access to learning, teaching, and professional development resources in digital format; and 3. standards, specifications, and guidelines for four (4) subsystem. The LRMDS serves as a clearinghouse that provides information about the location of resources (hardcopy and softcopy) and allows users to directly access digitized versions of resources published and stored within the LRMDS repository.

Republic Act 7796 which stated to reorganize initiatives to support and develop middle-level workers; adopt standards and tests for skills; create a system of accreditation for organizations working in this area; finance initiatives and programs for technical education and skill development; and technical education refers to the post-secondary and lower tertiary educational process that is officially recognized as non-degree programs and is intended to prepare technicians, paraprofessionals, and other categories of middle-level workers by giving them access to a wide range of general education, theoretical, scientific, and technological studies, as well as training in related job skills.

Figure 1. Research Paradigm of the Study

Statement of the Problem

This study aimed to determine the utilization of computer-aided instructional strategies for the Grade 9 learners in Technology and Livelihood Education skills in Second Congressional District of Schools Division Office I Pangasinan S.Y. 2023-2024.

Specifically, this study sought to answer the following sub- problems.

1. What is the profile of teachers teaching Technology and Livelihood Education in terms of:
 - Highest Educational Attainment
 - Field of Specialization
 - No. of Years of Teaching Technology and Livelihood Education
 - Relevant seminars/trainings attended?
2. What is the level of competency of the teachers in Information and Communications Technology as a component of Technology and Livelihood Education as perceived by the teachers themselves and the instructional leaders?
3. Is there a significant difference of the perception of the teachers and the instructional leaders?
4. Is there significant relationship between the level of competency in Information and Communications Technology of the teachers and their profile?
5. What is the level of utilization of computer-aided instructional strategies by the TLE teachers?
6. What is the level of performance of Grade 9 learners in Technology and Livelihood Education 9 after the utilization of the computer-aided instructional strategies?
7. Is there significant relationship between the level of utilization of computer-aided instructional strategies by the teachers and the level of performance of Grade 9 learners in Technology and Livelihood Education?
8. Based on the findings, what capability building program will be proposed to improve the academic performance of the learners.

Assumptions of the Study

1. Pretest and posttest are valid.
2. Computer-aided instructional strategies can be utilized to help Technology and Livelihood Education teachers improve the academic performance of the learners.
3. Capability building program can help improve competency level of teachers in Information and Communications technology (ICT).

Scope and Delimitation

This study was conducted in the Second Congressional District of Schools Division Office I Pangasinan during the School Year 2023 – 2024.

The variables that was investigated in this study focused on determining the performance of grade 9 learners in Technology and Livelihood Education after utilization of computer- aided instructional strategies for Technology and Livelihood Education, determining the different problems encountered during the utilization of computer-aided instructional strategies and the designed computer-aided instructional strategies in improving the academic performance of the learners and for adoption of Technology and Livelihood Education teachers.

Significance of the Study

Adequate instructional materials as well as the systematic implementation will help learners develop habits of mind that allow them to view the world through a critical scope. Repeated learner exposure to critical thinking practices will assist learners in all academic disciplines, as well as translate to life beyond high school.

Thus, this study will benefit the following:

Learners: It enables students to interact with educational material at their own pace, accommodating different learning preferences and capacities. Students can better understand and retain material when lessons include multimedia components like simulations, movies, and interactive quizzes. Additionally, the computer's quick response helps students develop their problem-solving abilities, correct misconceptions, and encourage self-

directed learning. The learners are the most significant aspect in the learning experience, the findings and observations generated in this study will serve as a guide to their own Technology and Livelihood Education learning.

Technology and Livelihood Education Teachers: It makes it simple for teachers to develop and distribute interesting lesson materials, promoting more lively and interactive learning settings. A teacher's function in the classroom is to be a catalyst, facilitator, monitor, and evaluator of the pupils' learning. Teachers must be aware of how their pupils perform, participate, and behave in class. It is critical that teachers analyze this study in order to guide pupils; additionally, teacher teaching may enhance upholding this information. Teachers may need to incorporate the knowledge gained from this study into the classroom.

Curriculum Planner: The result of the study can be used in planning and establishing significant activities for the effective Technology and Livelihood Education instruction.

Instructional Leaders: The findings of this study will serve as a call to action for administrators in terms of effective planning, direction, or guidance by encouraging instructors to utilize more applicable, appropriate, and effective methods and strategies that will improve their teaching abilities and performance. They may profit from this study because it will enlighten them on some strategies for enhancing their facilities and putting the proposed remedial efforts into action.

Parents: They will benefit greatly from computer-aided instruction since it gives them more insight into their child's academic achievement and encourages greater involvement in their learning process. Parents can easily get real-time information on their child's assignments, tests, and general performance through online platforms and communication tools, enabling them to be informed and active in their academic growth. Additionally, this technology promotes open communication between parents, instructors, and students, facilitating teamwork to support the child's academic objectives. Parents who have knowledge of their child's abilities and areas for development can provide encouragement, support, and direction that is specifically tailored to their child's needs, improving the home environment for learning.

Guidance Counselors: They will also be aided from this study by means of supplying those steadfast data of the verdicts for analysis and for guidance purposes especially in choosing the career path for learners.

Researcher: The results of the study would provide meaningful experience and insights in gathering and organizing data as well as for the improvement of teaching – learning process.

Future Researchers: The results of this investigation can be used as a tool or guide for the future researchers also from to conduct a study similar to the present research investigation.

Definition of Terms

To better understand this study and have a clear grasp of the terms used, the following terms are operationally defined.

Academic Performance. The achievement attained by the students in answering the test items prepared by the teacher that will be carried out in their pretest and posttest.

Computer-Aided Instructional Strategy. Such strategy will be utilized in this research investigation for the pursuit of improving their performance. CAI contain a wide range of additional educational materials, such as multimedia presentations, simulations, interactive exams, and virtual labs. These resources are all made to keep students interested, provide quick feedback, and support various learning styles. The application of CAI has the potential to transform conventional education by employing technology to create dynamic and learner-centered learning environments.

Grade 9 Learners. These are the learners attending high school education in the 2nd Congressional District of SDO1 Pangasinan. They are officially enrolled for the school year 2023 – 2024. They will serve as the main respondents in this research investigation.

TLE Teachers. These are the teachers teaching Technology and Livelihood Education in the Second Congressional District of Schools Division Office I Pangasinan. They will be part of the respondents in determining the problems encountered in the implementation of the computer-aided instructional strategies and its effectiveness.

TVL Teachers. These are the specialized teachers under Technical-Vocational-Livelihood Education that focuses primarily on teaching students in the industry work with the application of 21st century skills.

Second Congressional District of Schools Division Office I Pangasinan. It refers to the locale of the study wherein the teacher-respondents are currently teaching and wherein the Grade 9 learners are currently enrolled.

Instructional Leaders. It refers to any official accountable for the supervision or direction of an educational institution or system of an administrative unit this may comprises officials such as college or university presidents, deans, school superintendents, district supervisors, principal and head teachers. In this study, this includes the school heads, master teachers, head teachers, and subject area coordinators.

Chapter II

Research Methodology

This chapter presents the research design, sources of data, data – gathering instrument, data gathering procedures and statistical treatment of data.

Research Design: This study used the descriptive and developmental method of research that makes generalizations about a population based on a sample of data. This methodology allows researchers to test hypotheses and draw conclusions that allow them to predict patterns, behaviors, or outcomes that are not present in the current data set. The utilization of the computer-aided instructional strategies Creswell, 2014. The sources of data will be taken from the analysis of the responses of the respondents and the result of the test results and responses of the teachers from the given questionnaire.

Based on the analysis of the above results, the researcher developed computer-aided instructional strategies to improve performance of learners in Technology and Livelihood Education 9.

Sources of Data: This study was conducted in Second Congressional District in the Division of Pangasinan I, during the School Year 2023 – 2024. Quota Sampling was utilized in this investigation. There are 10 teachers and 10 learners allocated in each mother school within each of the Municipality of Second Congressional District in the Division of Pangasinan I with a total enumeration of 80 respondents TLE and TVL teachers, while 24 includes school heads, head teachers and master teachers.

Table 1 shows the distribution of respondents in the school.

Table 1: Distribution of the Respondents

2 nd Congressional District / Schools Per Municipality	Number of Teachers	Number of Instructional Leaders
A	10	3
B	10	3
C	10	3
D	10	3

E	10	3
F	10	3
G	10	3
H	10	3
Total	80	24

Table 2 shows the distribution of learner – respondents in the school.

Table 2: Distribution of the Learner - Respondents
N = 80

Schools Per Municipality	Number of Learners
A	10
B	10
C	10
D	10
E	10
F	10
G	10
H	10
Total	80

Instrumentation and Data Collection: There will be two set of data gathering instruments to be prepared by the researcher, the first one is the teacher-made test, an instrument that will be utilized in gathering data and information which is the pretest and posttest to determine the level of performance of the learners in Technology and Livelihood Education. Second, the validated questionnaire for the Technology and Livelihood Education teachers, including the TVL teaches, and instructional leaders regarding the utilization of the computer-aided instruction.

Prior to the start of gathering information and data which will be needed in the present investigation the researcher will seek permission from the Office of the Institute of Graduate and Professional Studies in Lyceum Northwestern University for the signing of the permit to conduct study duly attested by the research-adviser and it will be immediately followed as the researcher seek approval from the office of the Public Schools District Supervisor and Schools Division Superintendent for the conduct of the study, as the researcher needs Grade 9 learners and Technology and Livelihood Education teachers.

The researcher personally administered the pretest for the grade 9 learners and the research questionnaire for the Technology and Livelihood Education teachers to ensure smooth flow of this research investigation. Consent forms was also be provided for privacy purposes of their responses. The researcher personally makes the rounds in the collection of the test questionnaire for the learners and questionnaire of the teachers in order to ensure 100 percent retrieval.

After retrieval, the data will be tallied, organized, and presented in tables for analysis and interpretations.

Tools for Data Analysis: In order to elicit significant results and findings, appropriate statistical tools were employed in the analysis of the data.

For sub-problem no. 1, On the profile of the respondents, frequency and percentage was used. The formula is:

Where:

$$P = \frac{f}{n} \times 100$$

P = percentage
 n = number of particular groups
 f = total number of items

For sub - problem no. 2, On the competency level of teachers in ICT in Technology and Livelihood Education, average weighted mean was used. The competency level of teachers in ICT was described using a 3-point scale as shown below:

Scale	Point Range	Descriptive Equivalent
3	2.84 – 3.00	Expert (E)
2	1.67 – 2.83	Advanced (A)
1	1.00 – 1.66	Basic (B)

For sub-problem no. 3, On determining the significant difference of the perception of teachers and the instructional leaders, cross tabulation was used.

For sub-problem no. 4, On determining the significant relationship of the perception of teachers and the instructional leaders with their profile variables, cross tabulation was used.

For sub - problem no. 5, On determining the level of utilization of computer-aided instructional strategies average weighted mean will be used and a four lickert- scale and its descriptive equivalent as shown below.

Scale	Point Range	Descriptive Equivalent
4	3.25-4.00	Always Practiced
3	2.50-3.24	Moderately Practiced
2	1.75-2.49	Slightly Practiced
1	1.00-1.74	Not Practiced At All

For sub-problem number 6, On the level of performance of Grade 9 learners in Technology and Livelihood Education 9 after the utilization of the computer-aided instructional strategies, mean percentage score was used.

$$MPS = \frac{\text{Total Score}}{\text{Total Population}} \times 100$$

For sub - problem no. 7, On significant relationship between the computer-aided instructional strategies utilized by the teachers and the level of performance of Grade 9 learners in Technology and Livelihood Education, Spearman Coefficient Correlation was used.

$$r_s = 1 - \frac{6 \sum D^2}{N^3 - N} \quad \text{where: } r_s - \text{Spearman rho}$$

$\sum D^2$ - Sum of the squared difference between ranks

For sub - problem no. 8, On what Capability Building Program can be proposed to improve the performance of the learners, the researcher will develop and propose a Capability Building Program to improve the learners' academic performance.

Ethical Consideration: As a form data-privacy is concern, all actions pertaining to personal information and identity of all involved in this investigation will be kept confidential. This study investigation assures all will keep all responses concealed. As a result, participants will be advised not to include any personally identifiable information in their questionnaire or test material. Their responses will likewise be kept confidential. To preserve each subject's identity, the researcher will keep their information confidential; all information acquired from the study will be coded. No names or other identifying information will be used while discussing or reporting data. The researcher will securely preserve any files and data gathered. Once the data has been completely analyzed, it will be discarded.

Chapter III

Presentation, Analysis and Interpretation of Data

This chapter presents the analysis and interpretation of data gathered through the questionnaire.

The data are composed of the profile of the TLE teachers and instructional leaders in terms of highest educational qualification, seminars/trainings attended in TLE, years of teaching experience and field of specialization. Primarily the level of effectiveness of using computer-aided instructional strategies of TLE teachers as perceived by themselves and instructional leaders is analyzed as well as the differences of perception of the two groups of respondents. Included in the analysis are the relationship in the level of effectiveness of using computer-aided instructional strategies by the TLE teachers teaching TLE and determining also the performance level of TLE learners applying the aforementioned strategy.

Profile of the Respondents: Table 3 presents the different profile of the respondents in terms of highest educational qualifications or attainment, field of specialization, years in teaching TLE and, seminars/trainings attended in TLE.

Table 3: Profile of the Respondents in terms of Highest Educational Qualifications
N = 80

	Frequency	Percentage
Doctorate Degree	21	26.25
Master's Degree	43	53.75
Bachelor's Degree	16	20.00
Total	80	100.0

Table 3 above reveals that 16 of the respondents are bachelor's degree holders, Master's Degree holders are 43, and with finished Doctorate Degree Programs with an enumeration of 21. Teachers have met the basic educational qualification. This simply implies therefore they are qualified to teach the subject.

ICT-related degrees, as emphasized by the European Commission, not only enhance career and employment opportunities, but they also support digital literacy, boost productivity, and advance economic growth and competitiveness in the digital era (European Commission, 2018).

Table 4: Profile of the Respondents in terms of Field of Specialization
N = 80

	Frequency	Percentage
Filipino	1	1.25
English	1	1.25
Mathematics	0	0.00
Science	6	7.50
TLE	67	83.75
MAPEH	1	1.25
Social Studies	2	2.50
EsP/Values Education	2	2.50
Total	80	100.00

Along the field of specialization, it could be garnered that 67 of the teacher respondents are TLE majors, 6 are Science majors, two (2) social studies majors, and 2 are EsP/Values Education majors, in Filipino, English and MAPEH one for each subject, and none (0) Mathematics majors. This finding reveals that there is mismatch that happens in the teaching of the subject. Though, TLE majors were not outnumbered.

Table 5: Profile of the Respondents in terms of Years of Teaching Experience**N = 80**

Scale	Frequency	Percentage
21 years and above	3	3.75
16 – 20 years	8	10.00
11 – 15 years	53	66.25
6 – 10 years	11	13.75
0 – 5 years	5	6.25
TOTAL	80	100

Table 5 reveals that 5 of the 80 respondents have teaching experiences from 0 – 5 years. Meanwhile, 11 out of the 80 total respondents responded to 6-10 years. Moreover, 53 have teaching experiences from 11 – 15 years, 8 responded for an experience of 16-20 years and lastly, 3 have teaching experience of 21 years and above. This simply implies that majority of the teacher respondents are still at the peak of the career delivery services to the clientele. The length of service has a great deal of importance to the growth and status of teacher and that gives effort on her teaching. As Macomber (2004), pointed out that each a year of experience a teacher's professional competence in teaching increases and improves.

Table 6: Profile of the Respondents in terms of Seminars/Trainings Attended**N = 80**

Number of Relevant Seminars/Trainings Attended	Frequency	Percentage
10 and above	1	1.25
7 – 9	6	7.50
4 – 6	61	76.25
0 – 3	12	15.00
TOTAL	80	100

Along seminars and trainings, it could be gleaned that 61 of the respondents attended 4-6 numbers of seminars and trainings 12 have attended 0-3 numbers of seminars and trainings, 6 out of 80 attended 7-9 numbers of seminars and trainings and one (1) for 10 and above seminars and trainings.

The findings mean that their seminars and trainings are narrower in scope and could even be limited in topics as most of these trainings given are being re –echoed seminars/trainings. It could employ further that the teachers don't have the best opportunity to attend seminars/trainings for the advantage of all stakeholders, apparently, due to the financial constraints, related school activities, and administrative factors. This also implies that there are rare trainings and programs offered to teachers.

In order to close the digital gap, provide people the skills they need to participate fully in the digital society, and foster socioeconomic progress, the International Telecommunication Union (ITU) has underlined how important it is to fund ICT training programs (ITU, 2019).

Level of Competency of Technology and Livelihood Teachers in using Information and Communications Technology: Table 7 aptly presents the level of competency of TLE teachers in using Information and Communications Technology.

Table 7: Level of Competency of Technology and Livelihood Teachers in using Information and Communications Technology
N=80

Indicators	Mean	Descriptive Equivalent
1. The teacher demonstrates mastery of the subject matter (explains the subject matter without relying solely on the prescribed textbook and able to integrate ICT in their area).	2.16	A
2. The teacher draws and shares information on the state on the art of theory and practice in his/her discipline through AVP and other computer-assisted instruction.	2.36	A
3. The teacher integrates subject matter to practical and technological circumstances and learning interests/purposes of students through ICT applications.	2.48	A
4. The teacher uses OER application such as Wondershare Quiz Creator in giving sufficient quizzes, examinations and other forms of evaluating students' progress.	2.24	A
5. The teacher demonstrates up-to-date knowledge and/or awareness in current trends, and issues of the subject through technological advancement using ICT.	2.41	A
6. The teacher sets definite standard for measuring students' performance in line with the 21 st century teaching and technological advancement,	2.38	A
7. The teacher uses an advance technology such as smart television and computer laboratories in the teaching-learning process.	2.40	A
8. The teacher uses an appropriate teaching method related to the subject matter.	2.24	A
9. The teacher utilizes the DCP facilities of the school in the delivery of their subject area.	2.43	A
10. The teacher considers diversity of learners in the application of the different teaching method using ICT.	2.46	A
Weighted Mean	2.36	A
2.84 – 3.00 Expert (E)	1.67 – 2.83	Advanced (A)
	1.00 – 1.66	Basic (B)

The above-cited table briefly discussed the level of competency of Technology and Livelihood Education in using Information and Communications Technology. It could be gleaned that; the over-all weighted mean is 2.36 which falls on Advanced category. This manifest further that teachers of Technology and Livelihood Education are capable enough in using ICT in their classes. An educator with proficiency in ICT may tailor instruction to each student's requirements and style, develop interactive classes, and use a variety of digital tools, resources, and platforms. Teachers can create deeper knowledge of the material, increase student motivation, and promote collaboration by incorporating ICT into their teaching techniques.

ICT also provides educators with the resources they need to plan classes, evaluate student performance, and analyze data. This enables them to appropriately track students' progress and adapt lessons to suit their needs. According to UNESCO (United Nations Educational, Scientific, and Cultural Organization), Information and Communications Technology (ICT) can improve education's relevance, equality, and quality as well as assist lifelong learning and sustainable development (UNESCO, 2019).

ICT literacy also makes it possible for educators to collaborate with colleagues, access and utilize vast repositories of educational resources, and benefit from online professional development opportunities. The European Commission has emphasized that educators must possess the requisite ICT skills in order to promote innovation, enhance the quality of education, and provide students with the tools they need to thrive in the digital age (European Commission, 2013).

Table 8: Profile of the Instructional Leaders

N=24

Education Attainment	Frequency	Percentage
Doctorate Degree	12	50%
Master's Degree	10	41.67%
Bachelor's Degree	2	8.33%
Total	24	100%
Field of Specialization	Frequency	Percentage
Filipino	2	8.33%
English	3	12.50%
Mathematics	5	20.83%
Science	5	20.83%
TLE	5	20.83%
MAPEH	2	8.33%
Social Studies	1	4.17%
EsP/Values Education	1	4.17%
Total	24	100%
Teaching Experience	Frequency	Percentage
21 years and above	8	33.33%
16 – 20 years	9	37.50%
11 – 15 years	5	20.83%
6 – 10 years	2	8.33%
0 – 5 years	0	0.00%
Total	24	100%
Number of Trainings	Frequency	Percentage
10 and above	2	8.33%
7 – 9	10	41.67%
4 – 6	5	20.83%
0 – 3	7	29.17%
Total	24	100%

The dataset provides a comprehensive profile of 24 instructional leaders, containing details on their number of trainings completed, degrees obtained, specializations, and years of teaching experience. Twelve instructional leaders hold doctorates, and ten hold master's degrees, making up the clear majority of highly qualified faculty members. Each instructional leaders and their specialty are evenly distributed throughout key subjects including science, math, and TLE, displaying a broad breadth of expertise. Most respondents are seasoned professionals with a depth of pedagogical skills, with over half having more than 16 years of experience. Ten educators have demonstrated their commitment to lifelong learning by taking part in seven or more professional development sessions. Nevertheless, a few have had little training, thus they might need.

Table 9: Level of Competency of Technology and Livelihood Education Teachers as Perceived by the Instructional Leaders in using Information and Communications Technology

N=24

Indicators	Mean	Descriptive Equivalent
1. The teacher demonstrates mastery of the subject matter (explains the subject matter without relying solely on the prescribed textbook and able to integrate ICT in their area).	2.53	A

2. The teacher draws and shares information on the state on the art of theory and practice in his/her discipline through AVP and other computer-assisted instruction.	2.18	A
3. The teacher integrates subject matter to practical and technological circumstances and learning interests/purposes of students through ICT applications.	2.72	A
4. The teacher uses OER application such as Wondershare Quiz Creator in giving sufficient quizzes, examinations and other forms of evaluating students' progress.	2.28	A
5. The teacher demonstrates up-to-date knowledge and/or awareness in current trends, and issues of the subject through technological advancement using ICT.	2.80	A
6. The teacher sets definite standard for measuring students' performance in line with the 21st century teaching and technological advancement,	2.33	A
7. The teacher uses an advance technology such as smart television and computer laboratories in the teaching-learning process.	2.19	A
8. The teacher uses an appropriate teaching method related to the subject matter.	2.52	A
9. The teacher utilizes the DCP facilities of the school in the delivery of their subject area.	2.73	A
10. The teacher considers diversity of learners in the application of the different teaching method using ICT.	2.19	A
Weighted Mean	2.45	A
2.84 – 3.00 Expert (E) 1.67 – 2.83 Advanced (A) 1.00 – 1.66 Basic (B)		

Table 8 above briefly discussed the level of competency of Technology and Livelihood Education teachers as perceived by the instructional leaders in using Information and Communications Technology. It could be gleaned that; the over-all weighted mean is 2.45 which falls on Advanced category. This manifest further that instructional leaders who directly observed teachers of Technology and Livelihood Education are capable enough in using ICT in their classes. This manifest a positive outlook of being part of the 21st century learning with the aid of ICT in their respective classes.

Significant Difference of the Perception of the Teachers and Instructional Leaders: The below table aptly discusses the significant difference of perception of teachers and instructional leaders on the use of Computer-aided instructional strategies.

Table 10: Difference Between the Perception of Teachers and the Instructional Leaders

Group	Expert	Advanced	Basic	Total
Instructional Leaders	16	7	1	24
Teachers	35	30	15	80
Total	51	37	16	104

Table 9 aptly discuss the cross-tabulation data provided creates strong evidence about the intergroup differences in the employment of computer-aided instructional strategies between the identified 24 instructional leaders and 80 teachers. On the instructional leaders' perception of the teachers' level of competency in ICT, 16 out of 24, or 66.7%, belong to the Expert level, 7 are in the Advanced category (29.2%), and only 1 at 4.2% is in the Basic level. On the contrary, an impressive 43.75%, 35 out of 80 teachers

are in the Expert level, representing a strong overall proficiency for the teachers; 30 are in the Advanced level (37.5%) and 15 are in the Basic level (18.75%).

Significant Relationship between the Teachers' Profile and their Level of Competency in Information and Communications Technology: The succeeding table discussed the significant relations between the teachers' profile and their level of competency in Information and Communications Technology.

Table 11: Relationship Between the Teachers' Highest Educational Attainment and Level of Competency in ICT

N = 80

	Expert	Advanced	Basic	Total
Doctorate Degree	7	10	4	21
Master's Degree	15	26	2	43
Bachelor's Degree	3	9	4	16
Total	25	45	10	80

It can be gleaned in the table above that individuals with a master's degree are more likely to be at the Advanced level compared to those with Bachelor's or Doctorate degrees. Doctorate holders have a relatively balanced distribution between Expert and Advanced levels but have a notable percentage at the Basic level. Bachelor's degree holders show a significant distribution at the Basic level compared to the other degrees, indicating they might need more support to reach higher proficiency levels.

The cross tabulation reveals clear trends in proficiency levels based on educational attainment. Individuals with Doctorate and master's degrees are more likely to be at the Expert or Advanced proficiency levels, with master's degree holders predominating in the Advanced category. Bachelor's degree holders, however, have a higher proportion at the Basic level, suggesting a need for further training or education to achieve higher proficiency. This analysis can help in tailoring educational programs and professional development initiatives to improve proficiency levels across different educational attainments.

Table 11.1: Relationship Between the Teachers' Field of Specialization and Level of Competency in ICT

	Expert	Advanced	Basic	Total
Filipino	0	1	0	1
English	0	1	0	1
Mathematics	0	0	0	0
Science	0	5	1	6
TLE	16	50	1	67
MAPEH	0	1	0	1
Social Studies	0	1	1	2
EsP/Values Education	1	0	1	2
Total	17	59	4	80

There are not many MAPEH, English or Filipino teachers and all those available are at the advanced level which implies that there is a need to increase staffing levels. Math has no teacher at all, which is very serious and needs immediate solution.

The cross-tabulation indicates significant trends in the teacher competency levels across subject areas. Additionally, TLE has most teachers who have strong competencies, also, in science has a remarkably good performance. However, there aren't many teachers in MAPEH, English, or Filipino, and those who exist are only at an advanced level hence showing that we lack adequate staffing.

Table 11.2: Relationship Between the Teachers' Years in Service and Level of Competency in ICT
N = 80

	Expert	Advanced	Basic	Total
21 yrs. and above	3	0	0	3
16 – 20	2	6	0	8
11 – 15	3	45	5	53
6 – 10	1	3	7	11
0 – 5	0	2	3	5
Total	9	56	15	80

Based on years of experience, the cross-tabulation shows that some patterns in teacher competency exist. Teachers who have spent over 20 years in the profession are most proficient, all having an Expert level. Moderately well-versed instructors are those with 11–20 years of teaching practice who mostly fall within Advanced category. An increased proportion of beginning educators—especially those with 0–10 years of experience—are Basic level representing a demand for more professional growth and support to enhance their performance. The outcomes of this study will help to focus targeted programs for teachers at different career stages.

Table 11.3: Relationship Between the Teachers' Seminars/Trainings Attended and Level of Competency in ICT
N = 80

	Expert	Advanced	Basic	Total
10 and above	1	0	0	1
7 – 9	5	1	0	6
4 – 6	8	50	3	61
0 – 3	1	7	4	12
Total	15	58	7	80

Teacher proficiency as is evident from the cross-tabulation is influenced by the training. The highest level of proficiency is shown by teachers who have had 7-9 seminars/trainings attended, most of them being at expert level. The teacher with more than ten years of experience, strong proficiency was exhibited in expert level; while for 4-6 seminars/trainings attended, teachers also demonstrated high levels of proficiency, predominantly at the advanced stage. However, there are some teachers who have attended 0-3 trainings who still have many teachers in their rank on the Basic scale thus calling for further support and development. With this analysis it will be possible to target specific activities aimed at supporting teacher's career progression and strengthen overall teacher competence.

Table 12: Level of Utilization of Computer-Aided Instructional Strategies
N = 80

Indicators	Mean	Descriptive Equivalent
1. The teacher applies flexibility in the current trends of modern teaching where teaching method is concern.	3.07	MP
2. Upgrade oneself in the development of teaching career applying the latest trends in educational technology.	3.86	AP
3. Updated oneself with recent developments in education most especially with the advent of technology.	3.81	AP
4. Uses interactive whiteboards to display multimedia content such as videos, web pages, and interactive activities.	2.74	MP

5. Integrates digital storytelling in TLE lessons where students create stories using multimedia elements such as images, audio and video.	2.08	SP
6. Create online discussion forums or platforms where students can share multimedia resources related to TLE topics.	2.31	SP
7. Include gamification elements such as interactive quizzes, educational games and online simulations to make lessons more engaging and interactive.	1.91	SP
8. Uses up-to-date computer applications to catch the attention of the learners and make teaching-learning more meaningful.	3.02	MP
9. Incorporate videos and visuals such as images, charts and infographics to improve understanding and engagement.	2.74	MP
10. Promotes equal opportunities to learners on the use of ICT by helping them achieve the required competencies in their learning area.	3.84	AP
Weighted Mean	2.94	MP

3.25-4.00 Always Practiced 1.75-2.49 Slightly Practiced
 2.50-3.24 Moderately Practiced 1.00-1.74 Not Practiced At All

The table above was based on the following: access to extensive knowledge libraries, individualized and interactive learning and transnational interaction among teachers & learners; and traditional teaching and learning approaches in education have greatly changed through ICT. For creating learning objectives, increasing student engagement, and preparing students for succeeding in a rapidly changing digital world, ICT provides various tools and resources (UNESCO, 2020). Range of these materials is wide starting from virtual reality simulations and educational applications up to interactive whiteboards as well as e-learning platforms.

ICT also enables data analysis as well as predictive modeling leading to the researchers’ ability to scrutinize big databases so as to identify patterns for developing new treatments or interventions into complicated medical situations. According to the World Health Organization (WHO), integrating ICT into healthcare could improve the delivery of healthcare services globally; enhance patient outcomes; strengthen health systems worldwide (WHO, 2021). The succeeding table 10 presents the level performance of the TLE learners. The data gathered revealed that respondents are on the learning level of mastered.

Table 13: Level of Learners’ Performance

N = 80

Performance	N	Mean	Mean Percentage Score	LEARNING LEVEL
	80	39.90	79.80	Mastered

Below 60 - No Mastery 61 to 74 - Not Yet Mastered
 75 to 89 - Mastered 90 and above - Highly Mastered

The performance of the students garnered 79.80 as mean percentage score. It signifies that the students mastered the learning competency. The specific skills that are needed in TLE is the hands-on application of theories. By providing students with the opportunity to explore, test, and acquire firsthand understanding of the topics and ideas they read about in textbooks or attend lectures, practical exercises help to foster experiential learning.

Practical skills also help people think critically, be creative, and be inventive as they tackle real-world problems and attempt many solutions until they find one that works. People acquire the technical know-how

required for success in a world that is changing swiftly via hands-on interaction with materials, equipment, and technology. They also build a curious, resilient, and flexible mindset (NASEM, 2018).

The table 14 below presents the relationship between the level of utilization of computer-aided instructional strategies by the teachers and the level of performance of Grade 9 learners in Technology and Livelihood Education.

Table 14: Relationship Between Learners' Performance and Level of Utilization of Computer – Aided Instructional Strategies

	Spearman Rho	Description	Sig
Level of Utilization of CAI	-.038	Slight, Almost No Relationship	.741

The level of utilization of computer-aided instructional strategies by the teachers was treated as a scaled variable by transforming the data in SPSS using the mean.

The significance of utilization of computer-aided instructional strategies is 0.741. It is greater than the alpha level of 0.05. This means that there is no significant relationship between the performance of the students and the level of utilization of CAI strategies applied by their teachers.

Chapter IV

Summary, Conclusions, And Recommendations

Presented in this chapter is a synopsis of the entire research process undertaken to attain the objectives determining the effectiveness of using the computer-aided instructional strategies by the TLE teachers, and of the inferred conclusions and recommendations for future research.

Summary: This study aimed to determine the effectiveness of computer-aided instructional strategies used by the Technology and Livelihood Education teachers in the Second Congressional District of Schools Division Office I Pangasinan. This study used the descriptive and developmental method of research to ascertain the utilization of the computer-aided instructional strategies. The sources of data will be taken from the analysis of the responses of the respondents and the result of the test results and responses of the teachers from the given questionnaire.

Tools that enable the researcher to develop the necessary information and details will be of utmost importance in this research. As this is Descriptive research, the study shall describe existing situations and conditions relative to the study which included a total number of 80 learner-respondents, 80 teacher-respondents, and 24 instructional leaders which are randomly selected. The needed data were obtained from the teacher- made assessments to measure the academic performance of the learners and a validated questionnaire. Thorough interpretation of the participants' answers shaped the findings of this study. After the gathering of data, the researcher able to find out the effectiveness of using the computer-aided instructional strategies by the TLE teachers and instructional leaders able to find out the performance level of the respondents.

Findings: The noticeable findings of the study are as follows:

1. Respondents of this investigation are 80 Technology and Livelihood Education learners, 80 teachers in TLE, and 24 instructional leaders who are randomly selected from the Second Congressional District in the Schools Division Office I of Pangasinan.
2. Data revealed that 43 of the respondents coming from the total of 80 are MA Degree holders, 67 are TLE majors, 53 are of 11-15 years of teaching experience, and 61 of them attended 4-6 seminars/trainings.
3. Data shows on instructional leaders showed that 22 out of the 24 respondents are highly educated, with a Doctorate or master's degree, 22 out of 24 have more than 11 years, 7-9 seminars/trainings, with 10 instructional leaders, but 7 instructional leaders have limited exposure to training, indicating there may be areas of growth where an increase can be made in ongoing professional growth.

4. The level of competency of Technology and Livelihood Education teachers is described as “Advanced” which means, TLE teachers have mastery in using the computer-aided instructional strategies which is a necessary tool in helping and improving the academic performance of the learners.
5. The level of utilization of Computer-Aided Instructional Strategies is described as “moderately practiced” with an average weighted mean of 2.94. This entails that teachers are capable and knowledgeable in using computer-aided instructional strategies.
6. The performance level of the learners in Technology and Livelihood Education was described as “mastered”.
7. There is no significant relationship between the performance of the students and the level of utilization of Computer-Aided Instructional strategies applied by their teachers.
8. A Capability Building Program was proposed to improve the performance of the learners.

Conclusions

Based on the result of the study, the following conclusions can be drawn out. The result of the investigation using questionnaire and test questions designed by the researcher was tell-tale sign that the learners need a certain amount of presence from different technology use in teaching and also with the active involvement of their teachers. Computer-aided instructional techniques, which improve student learning through more dynamic, personalized, and interesting training, are essential components of modern classrooms. These techniques make use of technology to give students immediate feedback and design individualized learning paths so they can advance at their own speed. Furthermore, studies have shown that these methods might improve students' academic performance and motivation levels.

It is also concluded that from the result of the study, the computer-aided instructional strategy is effective based on the increase of performance of the learners, and it is beneficial in improving the skills related to Technology and Livelihood Education of the learners. This fortifies the idea that involvement of the instructional leaders and teachers was necessary to exact change in the academic performance of the learners. And since the level of performance of the learners in Technology and Livelihood Education is described as “mastered”, it is therefore concluded that the computer aided instructional strategies as the platform use in this investigation in the different setting of educational learning modality is an effective tool and strategy in improving the performance of the students in Technology and Livelihood Education.

This strategy encourages teachers to share responsibilities, differentiate their instruction, and advance their careers. Teachers can maximize student success by employing computer-aided instructional strategies to foster a collaborative and inclusive learning environment.

Recommendations

The following recommendations are offered, to wit:

1. It is shown in this study that the main subject or respondents used in this investigation are the grade 9 learners, I thus recommend to the future researcher the participation of other grade levels as to the continuity and consistency of result is concern.
2. As part of the local of the study is concern, it is therefor recommended to broaden the scope of research setting as it will also focused on the different congressional districts.
3. With the findings of the study, it is likewise recommended to have a regular focus group discussion on part of the teachers in order to adopt the designed strategy by the researcher for the benefit of other grade level.
4. And to make the result of this study more conclusive, it is highly recommended to have further studies and more research regarding the topic to create a more holistic and clear view of the subject matter at hand.

Capability Building Program for Computer-Aided Instructional Strategies in Technology and Livelihood Education

Introduction: It is important to adapt computer-aided instructional strategies to meet the specific needs and dynamics of your classroom. The flexibility and ongoing assessment of student progress will help you refine and adjust your approach to maximize the benefits of computer-aided instructional strategies.

This capability training program is push through because the following are the purposes of computer-aided instructional strategies which revolve around creating an engaging, supportive, and inclusive learning environment where students can develop academic skills, social skills, and a positive mindset towards learning. This capability training program is the answer for the pursuit of addressing the problems met by Technology and Livelihood Education teachers especially for the performance of the learners. The teaching of scientific process and conceptualizing teaching and learner projects are considered today as a milestone to every teacher. Such achievements of our learners are much inclined because of the expertise of the teachers behind those success. This proposal may serve as steppingstone to further address such problems of our dear teachers.

Objectives: This capability building program for Technology and Livelihood Education teachers will be able to:

1. orient school administrators and teachers specially to imbibe the role of computer-aided instructional strategies;
2. augment the needs of teachers to alleviate their skills in addressing performance of the learners and improve teaching experiences; and
3. provide teachers an avenue of fulfilling their professional advancement through 21st century.

Venue: BASISTA NATIONAL HIGH SCHOOL

DAY 1

Time	Activity/Topic	Resource Speakers/Facilitators
8:00-8:30 A.M.	Arrival and Registration	BNHS TLE / TVL Teachers
8:31-10:00 A.M.	Overview and Updates about the TLE Curriculum for Junior High School under MATATAG Curriculum	EPS in TLE / TVL
10:01:10:30 A.M.	HEALTH BREAK	
10:31 A.M.- 12:00 NN	Computer-aided Instructional Strategies in Teaching TLE amidst Challenges	Department Head / Head Teacher in TLE
12:01-1:00 P.M.	LUNCH BREAK	
1:01-3:00 P.M.	Technological and Skills Development through Peer Tutoring and Computer Applications in Teaching TLE	PSDS Basista District
3:01-4:30 P.M.	21 st Century Skills in Education	School Head-in-Charge in TLE / TVL
4:31-5:00 P.M.	Open Forum	

DAY 2

Time	Activity/Topic	Resource Speakers/Facilitators
8:00-8:30 A.M.	Arrival and Registration	BNHS TLE / TVL Teachers
8:31-10:00 A.M.	Application of Think-Pair-Share in Teaching TLE / TVL focus Group Works	District TLE Coordinator
10:01:10:30 A.M.	HEALTH BREAK	

10:31 A.M.- 12:00 NN	Upgrading of Instructional Strategies, Teaching Techniques and Methods in TLE / TVL Instruction	CID Chief
12:01-1:00 P.M.	LUNCH BREAK	
1:01-3:00 P.M.	Open Forum and Submission of Output in Instructional Materials Making using OER (Open Educational Resources)	Training Management Team
3:01-4:30 P.M.	Distribution of Certificates	

References

- Baker, R. S., & Inventado, P. S. (2014). Educational Data Mining and Learning Analytics. *Learning Analytics: Foundations, Applications, and Trends*, 61-75.
- Clark, R. C., & Mayer, R. E. (2016). *E-Learning and the Science of Instruction: Proven Guidelines for Consumers and Designers of Multimedia Learning*. John Wiley & Sons.
- Creswell, J. W. (2014). *Research Design: Qualitative, Quantitative, and Mixed Methods Approaches* (4th ed.). Sage Publications.
- Daft, R. L., & Lengel, R. H. (1986). Organizational information requirements, media richness and structural design. *Management Science*, 32(5), 554-571.
- Deci, E. L., & Ryan, R. M. (2000). The "what" and "why" of goal pursuits: Human needs and the self-determination of behavior. *Psychological Inquiry*, 11(4), 227-268.
- Department of Education Order 76, Series 2011 – National Adoption and Implementation of the Learning Resources Management and Development System (LRMDS)
- Deped Order 78 Series 2010 – Guidelines on the Implementation of the Deped Computerization Program (DCP)
- European Commission (2013). *Opening up education: A support framework for higher education institutions*. European Commission. Retrieved from https://ec.europa.eu/education/policy/higher-education/doc/opening/com533_en.pdf
- European Commission (2018). *Digital skills and jobs coalition: The importance of digital skills in the modern workplace*. European Commission. Retrieved from <https://ec.europa.eu/digital-single-market/en/news/importance-digital-skills-modern-workplace>
- Garrison, D. R., & Kanuka, H. (2004). Blended learning: Uncovering its transformative potential in higher education. *The Internet and Higher Education*, 7(2), 95-105.
- Hodges, C., Moore, S., Lockee, B., Trust, T., & Bond, A. (2020). The Difference Between Emergency Remote Teaching and Online Learning. *Educause Review*. Retrieved from <https://er.educause.edu/articles/2020/3/the-difference-between-emergency-remote-teaching-and-online-learning>
- International Telecommunication Union (ITU) (2019). *The importance of ICT skills and training in the 21st century*. International Telecommunication Union. Retrieved from <https://www.itu.int/en/ITU-D/Capacity-Building/Documents/Publications/The%20importance%20of%20ICT%20skills%20and%20training%20in%20the%2021st%20century.pdf>
- Jones, A. & Harris, B. (2021). Innovative Teaching Strategies in the Digital Age. *Journal of Modern Education*.
- Kulik, J. A., & Kulik, C. C. (2002). Effectiveness of computer-based instruction: An updated analysis. *Computers in Human Behavior*, 7(1-2), 75-94.
- Levy, P. (2002). Interactive multimedia and learning: Realizing the benefits. *Innovation in Education and Teaching International*, 39(3), 197-204.
- Means, B., Toyama, Y., Murphy, R., Bakia, M., & Jones, K. (2010). *Evaluation of Evidence-Based Practices in Online Learning: A Meta-Analysis and Review of Online Learning Studies*. U.S.

- Department of Education. Retrieved from <https://www2.ed.gov/rschstat/eval/tech/evidence-based-practices/finalreport.pdf>
17. Moore, M. G. (1993). Theory of transactional distance. In D. Keegan (Ed.), *Theoretical principles of distance education* (pp. 22-38). Routledge.
 18. National Academies of Sciences, Engineering, and Medicine (NASEM) (2018). *Learning through citizen science: Enhancing opportunities by design*. The National Academies Press. Retrieved from <https://www.nap.edu/catalog/25183/learning-through-citizen-science-enhancing-opportunities-by-design>
 19. Palloff, R. M., & Pratt, K. (2013). *The Excellent Online Instructor: Strategies for Professional Development*. John Wiley & Sons.
 20. Piaget, J. (1950). *The Psychology of Intelligence*. Routledge & Kegan Paul.
 21. Republic Act 7796 Technical Education and Skills-Development Act of 1994” or the “TESDA Act of 1994
 22. Republic Act No. 10844 | GOVPH. (2016, May 23). Official Gazette of the Republic of the Philippines. <https://www.officialgazette.gov.ph/2016/05/23/republic-act-no-10844/>
 23. Siemens, G. (2005). Connectivism: A learning theory for the digital age. *International Journal of Instructional Technology and Distance Learning*, 2(1), 3-10.
 24. Smith, J. (2020). The Impact of Technology on Learning. *Education Journal*.
 25. Sweller, J. (1988). Cognitive load during problem solving: Effects on learning. *Cognitive Science*, 12(2), 257-285.
 26. UNESCO (2019). IITE Policy Brief: Digital technologies in education: Policies, purposes, and potentials. United Nations Educational, Scientific and Cultural Organization. Retrieved from <https://iite.unesco.org/policybriefs/digital-technologies-in-education-policies-purposes-and-potentials/>
 27. UNESCO (2020). Leveraging ICT to ensure inclusive and equitable quality education and promote lifelong learning opportunities for all. UNESCO. Retrieved from <https://unesdoc.unesco.org/ark:/48223/pf0000373246>
 28. Vygotsky, L. S. (1978). *Mind in Society: The Development of Higher Psychological Processes*. Harvard University Press.
 29. World Health Organization (WHO) (2021). Digital health. World Health Organization. Retrieved from https://www.who.int/health-topics/digital-health#tab=tab_1